

Dispensing Justice by Supreme Court with Special Reference to Curative Petition

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Abstract

In this paper a modest attempt has been made to not only to explain the wide ranging jurisdiction of our Supreme Court to dispense justice, but also to present its still more activist role which emerged in the form of Curative petition in order to ensure the last possible opportunity for complete satisfaction of the petitioner who remains dissatisfied with the presence of some error in the final judgment of the final court. The genesis of curative petition has been traced out here, and the conditions have been described under which this petition could be approached with all practicable reasonableness as this is not a regular petition but it must be utilised by the apex court in the rarest of the rare case.

Keywords: Curative Petition, Rarest of the Rare Case.

Jurisdiction of Supreme Court Explained

When we look to the provisions of Indian Constitution⁽¹⁾ regarding its jurisdiction, we find it is very wide and all-embracing to not only entertaining matters under its original jurisdiction, but also to entertain matters for the enforcement of fundamental rights under its extra- ordinary jurisdiction under Article 32. It (Supreme Court) even enjoys appellate jurisdiction under Articles 132, 133, 134 and 134A of the Constitution. Article 136 has wide powers relating to Special Leave Petitions. Under Article 143 of the Constitution the apex Court can well advise the President of India. Article 137 gives more power to Supreme Court to review its very own judgments. There is one more prominent Article of Indian Constitution, that is Article 142 which is meant for providing complete justice and hence it gives inherently very potential scope for meeting the ends of justice, and for this it can devise any reasonable means and methods which may prove helpful to prevent the miscarriage of justice.

Activist Apex Judiciary : A Result of Apathy of Legislature

In the past, the functioning of the Indian Legislature had been very haphazard and not upto the mark on many occasions satisfying the growing problems of a young democratic nation. legislature was expected to streamline the legal system by introducing the laws which could help remove 'poverty', laws that could remove 'corruption' from the country, the laws that could effectively deal environmental matters around 1980s and 1990s. This is the period when Indian Supreme Court rose to the occasion and started playing activist role through Public Interest Litigation or Social Action Litigation taking the peoples' causes seriously enough.⁽²⁾

Here the following words⁽³⁾ of Supreme Court of India are catchy:

"The role of judiciary merely to interpret and declare the law was the concept of bygone age. It is no more open to debate as it is formally settled that the Courts can so mould and lay down the law formulating principles and guidelines as to adapt and adjust to the changing conditions of the society, the ultimate objective being to dispense justice." Therefore, we see the spirit behind these words of apex court, being the ultimate court of adjudication and appeal, to go as far as possible in accessing to last possible opportunity to dispense justice to the party concerned.

Evolution of the Doctrine of Curative Petition

Again, in *Rupa Ashok Hurra vs. Ashok Hurra*, the question before the Supreme Court was whether an aggrieved person is entitled to any relief against a final judgment or order of the Court after dismissal of review petition either under Article 32 of the Constitution or otherwise. Following the rule of *ex debito justitiae*

(meaning thereby, debt of justice), the Apex Court evolved the '**doctrine of curative petition**', which may be applied to rectify the error in the rarest of the rare cases, and to administer real justice to the party or parties concerned in the fairest possible manner.

Pre-conditions to be Satisfied Before Such Curative Petitions

First, a petitioner must ensure : (a) violation of principles of natural justice in that he was not a party to the lis but the judgment adversely affected his interests or ; (b) if he was a party to the lis he was not served with notice of the proceedings and the matter proceeded as if he had notice; and (c) where in the proceedings the learned Judge failed to disclose his connection with the subject matter or the parties giving scope for an apprehension of bias and the judgment adversely affects the petitioner. The petitioner shall also mention in the curative petition that the grounds (a) to (c) had been taken in the review petition and that it was dismissed by circulation. Besides, the curative petition must contain a certificate by a Senior Advocate with regard to the compliance of the above requirements. If the certificate does not specifically set out grounds for entertaining the curative petition, the Court will not entertain the petition.⁽⁴⁾

Justice-Oriented Approach : Need of the 21st Century

Exercising its inherent power, the apex Court admits the curative petitions in order to prevent abuse of process and to diminish the possibility of miscarriage of justice. Again, in **Rupa Ashok Hurra vs. Ashok Hurra case**, Justice U.C. Banerjee has remarkably justified the necessity of curative petition in the following words⁽⁵⁾ : “**procedural justice system** should give way to the **conceptual justice system** and efforts of the law Court ought to be so directed and “**justice oriented approach**” is the need of the day to strive and forge ahead in the 21st century.”

Support for the Doctrine of Curative Petition

The doctrine of curative petition has not only booked the support from senior lawyers and also the Attorney General. The petition also listed support in foreign jurisdiction. The Court aptly observed about the probable infallibility of curative petition in these words : “..... we are of the view that though Judges of the Highest Court do their best, subject of course to the limitation of human fallibility, yet situations may arise, in the rarest of the rare cases, which would require reconsideration of a final judgment to set right miscarriage of justice complained of. In such case it would not only be proper but also obligatory both legally and morally to rectify the error.” These wise words of the apex judiciary clearly manifests the fair intention on the part of the final court to deliver justice in the just and fairest manner in the rarest of rare cases, rather than giving priority to the policy of certainty of judgment.

Legally and Morally Obligatory : To Rectify the Error of Judgment

While formulating the doctrine of curative petition, the Constitution Bench in Rupa Ashok Hurra case, got support from the lawyers including the Attorney General. It also got support from foreign jurisdictions. Where, on the one hand, the question of finality and certainty of the judgment of final court was not easy enough to be ignored, the bare fact remains that still the chances of miscarriage of justice cannot be overlooked, despite the fact the Apex Court possesses such wide powers that no other court in the world do possess. Again, what is the sure guarantee that a curative petition will always be infallible.

Despite the strong arguments advanced for such a review as stated above regarding the guarantee of infallibility of curative petitions, the court still observed :

“Almighty alone is the dispenser of absolute justice — a concept which is not disputed but by a few. We are of the view that though Judges of the highest court do their best, subject of course to the limitation of human fallibility, yet situations may arise, in the rarest of the rare cases, which would require reconsideration of a final judgment to set right miscarriage of justice complained of. In such case it would not only be proper but also obligatory both legally and morally to rectify the error.”

So, we see that through this new judicial tool devised by Supreme Court in the form of curative petition to secure real justice to the party in need. But there is one negative impact this petition may have, as there are innumerable pending cases not only in Subordinate Courts of the country but also High Courts and Supreme Court are also victims of delayed justice. To avoid such a situation of delay due to arrival of this new petition, it is to be circulated first to a Bench of three senior most Judges. It is only when a majority of the learned Judges of this Bench (Three plus those who passed the impugned judgment) concludes that the matter needs hearing that it should be listed before the same Bench (as far as possible) which may pass appropriate orders.

Therefore, it is quite clear that the curative petition remedy is not a general remedy. At the same time, there is no fixed criterion to determine which particular case would fall in this category. To qualify for entertaining such a petition will be decided on the ground that a case has already gone through multi-stages of reviews and appeals to become **prima facie** to be a rare case. So, the requirements for entertaining such curative petitions are not rigid. The Court very assertively says⁽⁶⁾, “It is neither advisable nor possible to enumerate all the grounds on which such a petition may be entertained.”

Concluding Observation

At present, the real concern is of the misuse of this innovative device, and to curb this high probable menace may be answered by offering this remedy to check the petitions without merit or the petitions which are vexatious, and this may be done through stringently imposing some extraordinary and exemplary costs on the petitioner so that the justice process is not hindered frequently and goes ceaselessly. Now, only the future knows about the fate of this petition through its working experiences likely to be encountered by all the parties concerned.

References

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3. Rupa Ashok Hurra vs. Ashok Hurra, AIR 2002 SC 1771, 1786
4. N.T.P.C. Ltd. vs. Karri Pothuraju, AIR 2005 SC 4288
5. AIR 2002 SC 1771, 1796
6. AIR 2002 SC at 1789

